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“Let Brotherly Love Continue” (Hebrews 13: 1-3) Leveraging the Philadelphia Anthropocentric Approach for Ethnic Pluralism and Conflict Resolution in Nigeria

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Abstract

Assortment of ethnic groups gives Nigeria a rich array of culture, but poses challenges to growth, security and peaceful co-existence. Ethnic strife has plagued Nigeria since independence, creating fear of marginalization, nepotism, etc. Nigeria had a federation of three regions (Northern, Western and Eastern) at independence and each had adequate landmass, population and resources to become separate independent nation. Most ethnic conflicts are traceable to some degree of selfishness, pride, nepotism and disregard for the well-being of others. Exegetical, hermeneutical, historical and qualitative research methods were employed in this paper. The theoretical framework is based on Smith’s “monopoly of power by one cultural section”, which is the essential precondition for maintenance of the plural society in its current form. Any of the plural units, or its coalition, can have access to state control and use of power through constitutional process. This paper advocates that a *Philadelphia*-anthropocentric approach (that is, socio-theological approach for brotherly love) should be applied to the national life of Nigerians. The paper reveals that the advocacy for brotherly love among Nigerians- home and abroad regardless of religious affiliation, sex, ethnicity, background and political affiliation will encourage true nationality. Furthermore, genuine acceptability of the nation’s multicultural diversity will enhance societal integration and realignments. Conclusively, Nigerians pluralism, ethno religious diversities and the array of multicultural differences should be her selling point socially, politically and economically. Therefore, religious, community and socio-political leaders should consistently and deliberately inculcate the *Philadelphia*-anthropocentric approach in advocating for brotherly love in every sector of Nigerian society. This will militate against the incessant conflicts in Nigeria.

Keywords: Nigeria, Ethnicity, Pluralism, immigration, brotherly love, Exegesis of Hebrew 3:1-3, Philadelphia-anthropocentric approach

Introduction

Pluralism has both structural and cultural dimensions, and derives from such phenomena as conquests, forced labour, voluntary and involuntary immigration into host society. Varieties of pluralism exist in almost all societies. Nigeria is a highly pluralistic, complex, multi-ethnic, multi-lingual, multi-cultural and multi-religious entity (Idahosa, 2013). As a nation, it is demarcated along the lines of religion, language, culture, ethnicity and regional identity (Schwartz, 2013). By population, it is a nation of over 200,962,417 million people, with almost half Christians and half Muslims, aside other religions (Worldometer, n.d.). In recent years, the nation has been caught in series of ethno-religious violence fuelled by two dominant religious groups: Christianity and Islam (Paden, 2008). As noted by Huntington (1996):

Peoples and countries with similar cultures are coming together. People and countries with different cultures are coming apart. Alignments defined by ideology and super power relations are giving way to alignments defined by culture and civilization. Political boundaries increasingly are redrawn to coincide with cultural ones: ethnic, religious and civilizational... The question "Which side are you on?" has been replaced by the much more fundamental one, "Who are you?" Every state has to have an answer. That answer, its cultural identity, defines the states place in world politics, its friends and its enemies.

Ethnic pluralism as a factor underlying conflict remains a major problem in Nigeria; this has plagued Nigeria since her independence in 1960. The ethnic virus has been one of the most important causes of social crisis and political instability. Ethnicity has been perceived in general as a major obstacle to the overall political, social and economic development of the country (Danfulani & Atowoju, 2012). Lord Lugard's forced amalgamation of 1914, without a proper round-table agreement and subsequent British colonial policy of divide and rule instigated inter ethno-religious suspicion, residential segregation, hostility and antagonism among various communal groups (Oni, et al., 2008).

Today, Nigeria is plagued with some of the most obstinate conflicts, most of them constructed from differences in religious and ethnic identities. Religious and ethnic nationalism has led to conflicts about control of state power, unequal allocation of resources, marginalization, citizenship issues, state collapse, economic decline and ethno-religious clashes. Nigeria has been pushed hither and thither by recurrent crises of regional or state illegitimacy, often impairing efforts at economic transformation, democratic development, and security of life and property.

Nigerian society is seriously afflicted by cultural, economic and political diversities. Sadly, sufficient efforts have not been made to inculcate in the citizenry a sense of national consciousness, fundamental human right, acceptability of our unique differences and love for one another (Atowoju, 2018). Instead of emphasizing on those things that can unite the different entities, most leaders have sort to expend their energies and efforts on those things that differentiate the various ethnic groups, and often, the important weapons of disunity employed are religion and ethnicity. Hence, citizens tend to pledge their loyalty and allegiance to their ethnic socio-cultural group rather than Nigeria. The three largest and most dominant ethnic groups are *Ohanaese* (Igbo), *Arewa* (Hausa/Fulani) and *Afenifere* (Yoruba) traditional groups (Ajayi & Benard, 2013).

Recurrency of Violence in Nigeria

Nwankwo (2015) posited that Nigeria has experienced five successful coups, two abortive coups, one attempted coup and three alleged coups. The first and second coups were based on ethnic lines, which culminated in the Biafra war (the Nigerian civil war, 1967 – 1970), as the incompatible ethnic groups amalgamated by the then colonial administration opted for separatism. According to him, the seed of discord, division and ethnic nationalism in Nigeria is rooted in the legacies of colonialism. He noted that the existence of strong tribal, ethnic and religious ties, which causes the Nigerian people alienation from the central administrative powers, undermines the rhetoric about peace by government and religious groups. This is because despite attempts in religious and governmental groups' attempts to bring about peace in Nigeria, the local people's affection for their religion and ethnic groups displaces any love for central government. This type of ethnic and

religious composition in Nigeria appears to be making the development of a national identity almost impossible. It can also be argued that it accounts for the underdevelopment of the society.

Ethnicity, like religion, is an issue of primordial identity, and could easily be subjected to mobilization by actors for group cause (Ekwe, n.d.). Religion, on the other hand, is a very emotive issue. It is a matter of primordial identity and it means different things to different people. In some societies, it has taken ideological coloration to the extent that it provides a guide for faith, action and evaluation in private and public life; in others, it guides only private life. As noted by Yahaya, Bunnet opines that:

Religion for Nigerian people is a set of beliefs and practices based on faith, which are sacred and defy rational scrutiny. Therefore, it can quite easily trigger off emotional reactions. Religion also makes the world more predictable, the vicissitudes of life more tolerable and its complexities more understandable. It provides psychological relief and inspiration for the individual. At the social level, it provides a medium for fellowship and mutual support (Yahaya, 2011).

Ethnicity

Ethnicity has different definitions. Despres defined ethnicity as largely a subjective process of status identification. Hence, ethnic groups are formed to the extent that the actors use ethnic identities to categorize themselves and others for the purpose of interaction (Despres, 1975). In the view of Porter, most of the definitions accept the fact that ethnicity is an identity (Porter, 2011). He defines an ethnic group as a group of people whose members identify with each other through a common language, culture, religion, ideology or geographical area. For Sheppard, ethnicity is a concept, which was derived from the Greek word *ethnos* formerly posited on the foundation of national and cultural identity (Shepard, 1981). Horton and Hunt (1980) on the other hand, defined ethnic groups from a sociological point of view as a type of group that is socially identifiable as possessing its own separate sub-culture. In other words, ethnicity is conceived as a concept, which is an immensely complex phenomenon that portrays different perceptions. Osaghae (1992) opines that ethnicity is a social formation resting upon culturally specific practices and a unique set of symbols and cosmology. Different

bodies of literatures revealed that ethnic culture is one of the important ways people conceive themselves since culture and identity are closely intertwined. As a social construct, ethnicity can be regarded as the employment of ethnic identity and differences to gain advantage in situations of competition, conflict and cooperation.

Historically, Salawu (2010) points out that issue of ethnicity in Nigeria can be traced back to the colonial mistakes that forced the different ethnic groups of northern and southern provinces into becoming an entity called Nigeria in 1914. In 1947, Nigeria splits into three main political and ethnic groups: the north, made up of Hausa-Fulani, the west, made up of the Yoruba and the east made up of the Igbo among others. Perhaps both the British administration and the Nigerian elites at the time could tell that Nigeria could not stand the test of time in unity. According to London Evening Standard (2014), this is the reason why in the 1960s, late Chief Obafemi Awolowo succinctly noted that Nigeria was a mere geographical expression – an assertion used in describing Italy by Prince Metternich (a towering figure in Europe diplomacy) in 1847.

Causes and Effects of Ethnic Plurality and Conflict on Nigeria

A. Causes

1. Economic disadvantages

Onayeikan (2010) argued, not without some justification that: The recurring violent conflict between the Hausa/Fulani settlers and the Beroms is not simply a matter of their religious differences, but that it has more to do with the competition for limited land and other economic resources in the area. Land and resources have been a major cause of conflict all over Africa and have often led to ethnic confrontation and conflicts. In a situation such as that prevailing in the Plateau area where Fulani herdsmen are pitted in competition for land against the Beroms, an indigenous group that is largely agrarian, the eruption of ethnic conflicts cannot but be inevitable without the intervention of the state to ensure that the legitimate demands of both ethnic groups are made. Therefore, in seeking to tackle the problem, Onayeikan feels that the federal and state authorities must demonstrate fairness to all parties concerned. Open partisanship in support of one party can only aggravate the situation and make peaceful resolution of the conflict more difficult.

2. Poverty/Unemployment

Poverty has been identified as one of the major causes of ethnic and religious conflict which has become a prevailing social and political ill bedeviling the nation. The poverty level most especially in the Northern part of Nigeria contributes to the high frequency of ethno-religious conflicts in the North. Physical poverty creates societal problems particularly when many people cannot afford their basic needs, which make them do anything to sustain themselves. Consequently, the poor youths (*Almajiris*) are manipulated with small amount of money and food to cause religious conflicts.

Various other causes have been identified as basis of ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria. Ngwoke (1986) reported that lack of adequate understanding and absence of sound doctrines within various religious groups have been proposed. Others blamed fundamentalism, bad leadership within the religious groups and unemployment (Sani, n.d.). Elaigwu (2004) opined that:

There is a large army of the unemployed ready to be used for odious jobs, which bring some income. Breaking and looting of shops during religious crises, armed robbery, political thuggery, banditry and other forms of crimes have virtually been 'legitimized' by the logic of imperatives of survival.

Given the current economic hardship and high level of unemployment, "armed youths for hire" are available at cheap cost. While the federal government 'deregulates' the economy, politicians 'deregulate' violence and the control of instruments of violence, which is supposed to be the monopoly of government. A hungry man easily turns out to be an angry man, and the use of these weapons can be dangerous to the state. The armies of the unemployed are always willing to find new jobs as bodyguards, assassins, and cannon-fodders in communal violence. The conspicuous consumption of political office holders (whose backgrounds were well known before they assumed public offices) amidst the abject poverty of the people, not only alienate, but generate hatred.

3. Politics and Politicians

Elaigwu asserted that there is enough evidence to show that a good number of ethno-religious conflicts are caused by politicians and political leaders (Elaigwu, n.d.). Some of these politicians have no constituencies from which to demonstrate their relevance except

through their narrow ethnic and religious groups. Unfortunately, however, a majority pollutes young children with their bigotry and copiously exhibit ethno-centric arrogance. Many of the ethno-religious conflicts in the North are generated or exacerbated by these groups. Since no commission of inquiry ever punishes them, they hide behind their ethno-religious curtains as untouchable, constantly brewing and dispensing new forms of violence.

According to Bonnet, the colonialists succeeded in dividing various tribes against one another in the country so that they could rule Nigerians easily, but before Nigerians could get to put things in order and come together as one people and a strong country, the politicians made matters worse (Hamza (2017). Bonnet did not spare the country's religious leaders. According to him, the country's religious leaders also have their share of the blame in this matter of ethno-religious conflicts. Many of them claim to be holy, when they are in fact devils in religious garb, and they mislead their followers to think that apart from their religion there is no other. What the religious leaders should know is that if God had wanted all human kind or people of the world to be Muslims only or Christians, it could have been so. Bonnet therefore called on government to take a serious stand towards bringing these conflicts to an end as they posed serious threats to the mutual co-existence of various tribes and communities in Kaduna State (Ibid.). Today, some of the conflicts in the country and in our various communities are for economic survival.

4. Leadership Ineptitude and Political Manipulation of Religion:

Makarfi opined that bad leadership at both macro and micro levels have played a major part in the escalation of ethno-religious conflicts particularly when adequate mechanisms to reduce their occurrence are not employed (Makarfi, n.d.). He further observed various other factors identified as potential sources of conflicts in Nigeria to include:

Land, space and resource availability, dispute over jurisdiction between traditional rulers, creation of Local Government Councils, ethnic and sectional competition over access to scarce political and economic resources, population explosion, pollution of cultural practices, social-territorial and political-economic inequalities and disabilities and religious fanaticism (Ibid.).

Uzor (2002), on the other hand, blamed the conflicts on the struggle for power. According to him, most of the crises might have started on a religious note, but which later exposed the political tensions that have been smoldering in the North. The struggle for power in Kaduna and Plateau States gave ethnic and religious conflicts a bloody execution. In the view of Kukah (2002), continued manipulation of religion by leaders as a tool for governance is culpable. Kukah asserted that leaders have realized the difficulty in trying to separate politics from religion and have continued to manipulate this as a tool for governance. Enwerem (1995) opined that some use these conflicts to advance their political interest, providing poor citizens with funds in order to promote such conflicts for their selfish ends, while Akpokpari (2004) identified absence of good governance as the root of the crises, especially in Kaduna and Plateau States.

5. Religious Proselytizing factors

Achunike (2007) identified wrong perception of other people's religions or their faith, wrong religious orientation/indoctrination and literacy level of religious adherents as possible causes of conflicts in the modern-day religious practices. In Gwamna's opinion, the root of religious conflict was planted in the 70s. This decade saw oil boom in the nation and the political elites had to use religion as a manipulating tool to create a dividing nation that will not be able to focus on serious political matters while using the chaotic state for their economic gains. Kukah (1993) blamed the conflicts on sentiments and emotions of worshippers, proliferation of religious sects, fanaticism, too much freedom given to religious leaders and feelings of marginalization, unpreparedness of some segment of the Nigerian society to respect the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria vis-à-vis the provision for religious affairs especially the Islamic legal system. Yaro (1988) is of the belief that the ugly elements that habitually generate conflicts among religious adherents are arguments over 'faith' and 'worship.' These are often times anchored on political emancipation, economic benefit, local prestige, cultural diversity and psychological imbalance. Mbiti (1986) identified the major causes of discords among adherent of the major religious groups in the areas of different moral requirements, initiation rites, marriage customs, offering connected to the dead, place of sorcery, evil

magic and witch-craft, methods of dealing with diseases, misfortunes and sufferings.

Eliade (1987) observed that, while Christianity is viewed as a product of America and European imperialism, Islam is believed to have emanated from the dominative exploits of the Arabian traders. For instance, the immediate outcome of the political factor, for religious and political conflicts is the economic benefits, which the big wigs of society anticipate to gain, through grants that will mount up to their private purse if only they can profess allegiance to one of the political or religious factions. Some of them will even make up arms to see to the perpetual domination of one political or religious group over the others.

Sani further asserted that “differences over values such as ideology and religion have also been some of the major causes of ethnic and religious conflicts in the past (Sani, 2007).” A good example of this is the year 2000 Kaduna religious conflicts which claimed many lives. The conflicts were allegedly sparked off by the protest against the implementation of Sharia legal system. This is because the Christians saw Sharia as an attempt to diminish the strength of Christianity. Over-zealousness of some religious devotees to their respective religions seems to have been making them to act in ways that are both immoral and contrary to the ethics of religions. It has made them kill, maimed and destroyed all in the name of God (Ibid.).

Onah (1996) is of the view that the deep-rooted and stereo-typed misconception about religion has caused serious lack of trust among the various religious groups. The proliferation of sects and cults among the various emerging religious orders has continued to encourage stereo-typed misconception and prejudices. This is because these sects and cults provide a helpful lens through which to observe and analyze distinction between healthy and corrupt religions. Soyinka witnessing the sharp intolerance of Muslim worshippers who called for the removal of a cross, the Christian symbol of faith in the University of Ibadan Christian Chapel some years back remarked that:

Violence appears to be the one constant thing in the histories of the major religions of the world, a primitive aggressive violence despite the lip-service which their tenets pay to the need for tolerance, peace and understanding Soyinka, (1991).

The above scenario to Soyinka’s close friend, though not a Christian who was bitter and not happy with the development vowed that if the

problem was not amicably settled between the Muslims and Christians, he was going to take a gun and shoot someone who will attempt removing the cross.

From the above expression, we can see that lack of tolerance of the beliefs and views of others, unguarded and provocative utterances or preaching by some religious leaders are some ways by which conflicts arise. Disagreement as a result of differences of opinion, misinterpretation and wrong perception between religious groups, blocking of roads by Muslims on Fridays during their prayers, unnecessary delays of non-Muslim passengers in commercial vehicles on roads for prayers, etc. could also be responsible for conflicts.

Usman (1987) looked at the manipulation of religion as another cause that makes those who feel oppressed to resort to religious conflicts as a way of expressing their grievances. Some tribes, groups and communities feeling alienated or unrecognized in the country, take their case to the government through religious conflicts. Sponsoring of religious conflicts between Christians and Muslims thus, becomes an avenue for some people to express their perceived marginalization to the government, taking an advantage of the non-cordial relationship between Christians and Muslims in the country.

Okwueze (2001) observed also that Muslim leaders in the country have acted and made assertions which lend credence to the fact that Muslims in Nigeria are intolerant towards non-Muslims. This was exemplified by the assertion of Safi Jimba, a Muslim and a prominent lawyer in Ilorin on the controversial Sharia issue where he was quoted by Okwueze to have said that “it is either we have the Sharia or there shall be no constitution or even peace in this country.” Also, late Sheik Abubakar Gumi, a prominent Muslim leader asserted that “the progress and unity of human race means converting Christians and non-Muslims to Islam.” These were all volatile statements loaded with intolerance. Okwueze is of the belief that Christians are not totally exempted from the issue of intolerance but they have been in most cases at the receiving end.

6. Constitutional Violation

Constitutional violation has also been identified as one of the grey areas that have continued to promote religious conflicts in Nigeria. This has on several occasions prompted the call for a Sovereign National Conference and structural adjustment because of the perceived

marginalization of a section of the country, and because of some religious issues and debates, especially regarding Sharia, OIC, and power-sharing among others.

7. Electoral Malpractice and Political Intolerance

Given the perception that the control of state power is important, groups often decide which political platform is the best for the pursuit and the promotion of their interests. Thus, politics in Nigeria is not game but a battle and political failure has been a major source of conflict. Similarly, the political intolerance of members of political parties generates intra-party and inter-party conflicts. At times, ethno-religious support is mobilized to achieve targets. In addition, the ‘*Tarzarcemania*’ (or self-succession) of political incumbents generates conflicts as there are often zones or groups which are opposed to the self-succession of the incumbents.

8. Non-Implementation of Conflict Reports by Government

It is believed that the failure by government in the implementation of conflict reports sometimes encourage ethno-religious conflicts in the country.

9. Poor Security Network

The causes of conflicts can also be attributed to inadequate or poor security network. Government sometimes does not provide security at the right time during crises. In potential conflicts situations, security agencies may be useful in creating a sense of safety and security among groups.

10. Poor Standard of Education

Kukah noted that one of the reasons for conflicts in Northern Nigeria is the poor standard of Western Education and Civilization (Kukah, n.d.).

B) Effects of Ethno-Religious Crises

1. Effect on lives and properties

Ethno-religious conflicts have resulted in the destruction of property and death of several of hundreds of thousands of people, men and women. The conflicts have resulted in the irreparable loss of human

resources that could have been used for developmental purposes. The sad elimination of the breadwinners of such families led to increase in begging, prostitution and unemployment. Sadly still, where both parents were eliminated, the children (boys or girls) were forced to assume parental roles at tender ages, which also have its negative social implication. In most cases, the wounds left in the psyche of these people might not be obvious, but are often said to be mentally, psychologically and emotionally far reaching. These children may grow up with their minds fixed on hatred and set for revenge. No meaningful social development can thrive under the circumstances of religious crises.

2. Effect on political and economic development/industrialization

Ethno-religious crises have contributed to the weakening of the nation's economic development. The statistical breakdown of personnel and material resources wasted in Kaduna State alone can, in a glance give insight into what Nigeria has lost to ethno-religious crises. Ahmadu Bello Way, Kaduna, by all standards is one of the most beautiful streets in Northern Nigeria that houses business shops and political offices. Car Malls and financial institutions equally jostle for accommodation along the road. A peaceful protest match by Christians against plans to adopt Sharia ignited violence and carnage, which turned out to be the worse in the history of the State and the nation in general (Tell, 2000). The material and human resources wasted from February 20 to 24, 2000, include, many shops, which were burnt down by the rioters. About 300 houses and shops at the Abuja junction Garage, Charity Hotel and Rakiya Memorial hospital as well as Magistrate Court were destroyed. Forty-five fuel tankers were burnt down. Not less than 200 houses were burnt in Barnawa located in the South Eastern part of Kaduna. Fifty business shops between Leventis roundabout and Katsina road were burnt down. Fifty-million-naira worth of goods in Labaran Ali Electronics Store was burnt down and about sixty-million-naira Electronics and building material shops on the same Ahmadu Bello road were destroyed. Vehicles worth millions of naira and constituting means of livelihood to some people were also destroyed during the crises. For example, Ikara Motors lost about fifty assorted fairly used cars, buses and trucks each valuing not less than N350, 000. In Television Garage, Kaduna, 18 vehicles were destroyed and at Abuja junction Garage, 51

vehicles were also destroyed. Many churches, 123, 50 mosques and about 1000 houses were also burnt down at Tirkania-Nasarawa, Ungwar Muazu, Kabala West, Rigasa and along Lemu road in Tudun Wada, Kaduna (Ibid.). The 2000 February ethno-religious crises in Kaduna did not allow some foreign investors who came into the state to invest in the Agricultural sector to do so. Instead, they were abruptly ferried out of the state by security agents.

The same crises led to the shifting of that year's Kaduna Trade Fair a week further. Despite the shifting, several foreign participants who had earlier indicated their interest to be at the fair hurriedly cancelled their participation. Kaduna State that was fast becoming an industrial centre suddenly lost that status. To that effect, several direct air flights to Kaduna State and other States in the northern part of the country were cancelled. These crises made both local and foreign investors see Nigeria as "no go area" that is full of risk and uncertainties in establishing business. Ethno-religious crises discourage growth in the sense of industrialization. This is because; no businessman or industrialist would want to invest where the safety of their investment is not guaranteed.

In addition, ethno-religious crises have serious consequences on the nation's political development. It affects our democratic values and norms and also delays viable political transition and consequently decimates the aspiration of producing a nation state. The Nigerian political evaluation has been characterized by periodic instability instigated mostly by the elitist manipulation of religion as a survival strategy. Religious membership and association rather than the political parties selected these candidates for elections. These have also contributed to the electoral violence that we have witnessed in the past and in these recent years. For instance, in the 1964 general elections, the violence instigated led to the 1966 military coup and political instability, which culminated in the civil war. Yet, the violence occurred in 1983, 2003, 2007 and even in the 2011 general elections. These are obvious indications that politicians have not learnt any lesson from their mistakes of the past. Most politicians are particular about the issue of who takes what, rather than how democratic norms and values would be entrenched in the nation. The political future of the country depends on the level of which the various religious components can tolerate themselves.

The religious polarization of Muslims and Christians poses serious challenges to democratization in Nigeria. It is the obvious instability and deficiency in the democratic process that prompted religious and ethnic nationalism. It has resulted in the emergence of socio-cultural groups like *Ohaneze*, *Afenifere* or *Oduduwa* movement and the *Arewa* Consultative Forum (ACF). These groups now act as political platforms to actualize the aspiration of their adherents. This has prompted Muslim fundamentalists craving to convert Nigeria into a theocratic state governed by Sharia and also prompted Christian fanatics craving to convert Nigeria into a theocratic state governed by the Canon Laws. The above craves according to researchers; by both Christians and Muslims have serious security implication for the waves of religious violence in Nigeria. Money is wasted on litigation and out of courts settlements. Funds are also wasted in mobilizing and sustaining security operatives and the proliferation of small arms. Arms are now getting into wrong hands. Some of these arms are legally imported or smuggled into the country, or are violently acquired from law enforcement agents. Realizing the security implication of these arms getting into wrong hands, made the Federal Government established a task force to work towards retrieving such illegal arms.

Philadelphia Anthropocentric Approach: A Demand for Peaceful Co-Existence in Nigeria

Yahaya (2011) points out that the Christians and Muslims of whatever ethnic background had lived together peacefully for several years until 'outside' influences began to emerge. According to him "We had no problem until some forces from outside began to put ideas into the heads of our Muslim brothers on the need to Islamize the State or agitate for certain rights and since then, we have not known peace," he alleged (Yahaya, 2011).

Today, Salawu writes that building a national identity is a daunting task in Nigeria. The three major ethnic groups: Hausa, Yoruba and Igbo and the numerous minority ethnic groups owe their allegiances to their tribes and faiths. For him, these large and divergent cultures as well as an unimaginable sense of tribal cohesion make it is impossible for Nigeria to claim a unified nationality. The effort to achieve national unity has often triggered social discord and conflict within the country. The reason being that the ethnic groups in the society often have the feeling, or

belief, that they are being dominated by other more powerful groups. The level of mistrust and fear of dominance that is inherent in the ethnic groups drives them to believe that they do not believe that they get proper representation at national level or that they get a fair share of the national cake. This is why the advocacy for “brotherly love in Hebrews 13:1-3 is imperative”.

Theologically speaking, most scholars generally regard the book of Hebrews to be second in order of importance only to Paul's letter to the Romans in the New Testament (Hoppin, 2009). No other book has eloquently defined Christ as High Priest who is superior to the Aaronic priesthood, and the fulfillment of the Law and the Prophets. Although the book of Hebrews quotes extensively from the Old Testament. Paul, as a Pharisee, would have been familiar with the Scripture in its original Hebrew language. The Epistle to the Hebrews was included in Pauline Corpus from a very early date. Church tradition teaches that Paul wrote the book of Hebrews, and this was the position until the 1800s, before arguments arose concerning the authorship (Heard, 2019). Nevertheless, a vast majority of Christians still believe Paul wrote the book, though there are compelling reasons to think otherwise (Guthrie, (2009). Arguments in favour of authorship by Paul cited the late second-century or early third-century codex 46, which is a volume of Paul's general epistles, which included Hebrews as Pauline epistle immediately after Romans (Comfort, 2005). The assumption of Pauline authorship of Hebrews encouraged its acceptance in the Eastern Church; however, this was doubted in the West (Mitchell, 2007). Doubts about Pauline authorship were raised around the end of the second century, predominantly in the West (Rothschild, 2009). Origen noted that others had claimed Clement or Luke as the author, but he tentatively accepted Pauline authorship and the explanation of Clement of Alexandria (Kirby, 2019). Priscilla and Apollos are other names included in the list of possible authors of Hebrews (Luther, n.d.). The book of Hebrews quotes extensively from the Old Testament. Paul, as a Pharisee, would have been familiar with the Scripture in its original Hebrew language. In other letters, Paul either quotes the Masoretic Text (the original Hebrew) or paraphrases it. However, all of the quotes in this epistle are taken out of the Septuagint (the Greek Old Testament), which is inconsistent with Paul's usage. Finally, Paul was an apostle who claimed to receive his revelations directly from the Lord Jesus (1 Corinthians 11:23; Galatians

1:12). The writer of Hebrews specifically says that he was taught by an apostle (Hebrews 2:3). Jerome, aware of such lingering doubts, included the epistle in his Vulgate but moved it to the end of Paul's writings (Eusebius, 1965; Keathley, 2018).

Augustine affirmed Paul's authorship and vigorously defended the epistle. The theology presented in Hebrews is consistent with Paul's. Paul was a proponent of salvation by faith alone (Ephesians 2:8, 9), and that message is strongly communicated in this epistle (Hebrews 4:2, 6:12, 10:19-22, 10:37-39, and 11:1-40); suggesting either Paul wrote the epistle, or the writer was trained by Paul. Further, although it is a small detail, this epistle makes mention of Timothy (Hebrews 13:23), and Paul is the only apostle known to have ever done that in any letter. The most compelling evidence that Paul wrote the letter comes from Scripture itself. Peter wrote to the Hebrews (Galatians 2:7, 9 and 1 Peter 1:1). "... just as our dear brother Paul also wrote you with the wisdom that God gave him" (2 Peter 3:15). In that last verse, Peter is confirming that Paul had also written a letter to the Hebrews (Attridge, 1989). In addition, the letter closes with the words "Grace be with you all" (Hebrews 13:25), which is the same closing found in each of Paul's known letters (cf. Romans 16:20; 1 Corinthians 16:23; 2 Corinthians 13:14; Galatians 6:18; Ephesians 6:24; Philippians 4:23; Colossians 4:18; 1 Thessalonians 5:28; 2 Thessalonians 3:18; 1 Timothy 6:21; 2 Timothy 4:22; Titus 3:15; and Philemon 25). However, it should be noted that Peter (1 Peter 5:14; 2 Peter 3:18) used similar – though not identical closings. Possibly, it was customary to close letters like these with the words "Grace be with you all" during the period (Girard, 2008).

On the other hand, however, there are strong evidences against Pauline authorship and in general, the available evidences are considered too solid for scholarly dispute (Heard, 2019). First and foremost is the lack of personal salutation as seen in all Paul's letters – writing anonymously is not Paul's usual method. Second, the overall composition and style is of a very sophisticated writer. Even though Paul was certainly a sophisticated communicator, he stated that he purposely did not speak with a commanding vocabulary (1 Corinthians 1:17; 2:1; 2 Corinthians 11:6).

In the year 61 C.E., the Christian congregations throughout Israel enjoyed a period of relative peace. However, Jesus prophesied that five years afterwards, Jerusalem would be "surrounded by encamped

armies”. In the 28 years after Jesus uttered the prophecy, the faithful Jewish Christians living in Israel had faced many opposition and persecution successfully (Heb. 10:32-34). However, they would need exceptional endurance and faith, strong enough to preserve their lives (Heb. 10:36-39). Consequently, the epistle to the Hebrews was written to those dear brothers and sisters to meet their special needs.

Nigerians today should be interested in the message directed to those first-century Hebrew Christians because we find ourselves in a similar situation. At that time, “their nation was miserably divided and distracted among themselves, both on the matters of religion and the civil state”, (Henry, 2016). Consequently, at the time of persecution, when brotherly love would be most necessary; it was in danger of being lost by those disputes that were among them; but this must be guarded against, and all proper means encouraged at preserving it (Ibid.). “Let brotherly love continue”, the author of Hebrews admonishes.

The Greek term used in Hebrews 13:1 is **Ἡ φιλαδελφία μενέτω** – “Let brotherly love continue”, **μενέτω**– is an indication that the love should abide and must cease not. For, according to Hebrew 6:10, 33, the recipients of the epistle had already imbibed this virtue, and were still exercising it. Yet, since a number of them have lost confidence and had become doubtful regarding the absolute truth of Christianity, and in part, already sought to withdraw from the outward fellowship of Christians (Hebrew 10:25) and in particularistic prejudice closed their hearts against a brotherly intercourse with the Gentile Christians, the renewed inculcation of this virtue was of special importance.

Φιλαδελφία (*phi-la-del-phi'a*), literally means “affection for a brother.” The Vulgate Latin and Syriac versions add, “in you”; or among you, as a church and society of Christians; for this is not to be understood of love to all mankind, or to those of the same nation. Brotherly love is the type of affection that involves a strong, warm, personal attachment, such as the relationship with a family member or a close friend (John 11:36). Richard Heard says, “We do not pretend to be brothers and sisters - we are brothers and sisters (Matt. 23:8). Our strong feeling of attachment to one another is summed up in these words: “In brotherly love, have tender affection for one another. In showing honour to one another, take the lead” (Rom. 12:10)” (Heard, 2019). In Judaism, the meaning of the word “brother” sometimes extended beyond those who were literally

relatives, but its meaning was still restricted to those within the Jewish nation and did not include Gentiles. However, Christianity embraces all people no matter what their nationality, sex or background is (Romans 12 cf. 1 Thess. 4:9).

How Can Brotherly Love Continue (Heb. 13:2 -3) in Nigeria?

“Do not forget hospitality.” (Hebrews 13:2.) The original-language expression translated “hospitality” means “kindness to strangers.” **τῆς φιλοξενίας μὴ ἐπιλανθάνεσθε**, “Entertainment of strangers, do not neglect”. This phrase reminds the Christians of the examples of Abraham and Lot. Both men showed kindness to visitors whom they did not know. These visitors turned out to be angels. (Gen. 18:2-5; 19:1-3). The author of Hebrews alludes to these examples in order to encourage the Hebrew Christians to show brotherly love by being hospitable. Mitchel says, “We would not need to make elaborate or expensive arrangements to be considered hospitable; nor would we want to invite only those who might repay us in some way (Luke 10:42; 14: 12-14). Our goal should be to encourage, not impressing (3 John 5-8)” (Mitchell, xxx). It was a special form of the more universal “love” (Ἀγάπη).

Love is one of the most important and distinctive of all Christian graces. The spirit of Christianity is a spirit of love. Brotherly love is a grace absolutely necessary. Faith works by love. So violent and irresistible is the power of love, that it will pass through all difficulties, and overthrow all obstacles. Amidst all imperfections, there is nothing so good and nothing as helpful as brotherly love - meek, generous, thinking no evil, seeking not its own, believing all things, hoping all things, enduring all things. Through love we must show, by contrast with the unsanctified human nature, that Christ's religion makes us gentle, kind, patient, and forgiving; and as Christ's history is the loveliest exhibition of divine love, so we must reflect the highest honour on our once crucified but risen Lord, by loving others.

Christ affirmed that brotherly love is the badge of true discipleship and has the potential to reflect His love for the world even to those who have not known Him or seen Him (John 13:34-35). How entirely this was fulfilled could be seen in the fervid descriptions of Tertullian, from the mocking admissions of Lucian in his curious and interesting tract “on the death of Peregrinus,” and from the remark of the Emperor Julian,

that their “kindness towards strangers” had been a chief means of propagating their “atheism”. No wonder Paul challenged his converts to love one another more and more (1 Thess. 4:9).

Truly, Christianity does not deprive one of his or her individuality (Biblical Illustrator, n.d.). With the same inspired truth, Nigerians differ, in their opinions as to the meaning or extent of that truth. Again, people are liable to have their preferences and prejudices as well as their opinions. However, here is the need for the exercise of that love "that thinks no evil"; that, in honour, prefers another to itself. Brotherly love accords to others what they claim for themselves, and more - for, in true humility, in honour the scripture says, "esteems others better than yourself." It is deferential, forbearing, and forgiving. To rejoice in the success of a brother, more than in one's own, is strong evidence that the person "has been with Jesus," and breathed largely of His Spirit. Love throws its wondrous power over sinful opposition, and with more than the skill of Orpheus. Love is the vitalizing principle of truth, experience and duty. It concentrates individual piety in intense beauty in the character of the Church, while it unifies and employs all the strength of the Church in its sacred mission on the earth. Brotherly love is magnetic. It is the great law of gravity in God's spiritual universe; it binds each orb and keeps it coherent (Ibid.). The author of Hebrews urges - "Let brotherly love continue." Disputes about religion too often produce a decay of Christian affection; but this must be guarded against (Henry, 2016). Christians should always love and live as brethren; irrespective of their differences and the more they grow in devout affection to God, the more they will grow in love to one another and people of other faiths for His sake.

Conclusion

When **Φιλαδελφία** is genuine, it expresses itself in bearing one another's burdens, forbearing and forgiving one another, admonishing one another in love, building up each other in the most holy faith and stirring up one another to the several duties of religion. Without this excellent and useful grace, a profession of religion is in vain because love is the evidence of our regeneration; it is the bond of perfectness and it is what renders the saints' communion delightful and edifying.

The Nigerian situation demands that the various religious and traditional groups desist from fanning the embers of war or sowing the

seeds of fear in our various communities. The merchants of violence and ethnic and religious entrepreneurs must give peace a chance. The critical stakeholders must show empathy to the sufferings of the people that have lost loved ones, their homes and their properties. In other words, the present conflict situation in Nigeria must be deescalated and civil society organizations and professional groups and associations must show leadership in this direction. Professional groups and civil society organizations must rise above the dominant sentiments that have blotted the middle ground and must keep the middle ground open by serving as a voice of moderation. Each religious and ethnic group must deliberately inculcate the culture of *philadelphia*-anthropocentric as found in the message to the Hebrews. This will bring about a lasting peace in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Emphasis should be placed on love, tolerance, cooperation, sharing and acceptability among the citizens of Nigeria.
2. Since poverty has been noted as chief among the instigators of social conflict, economic development needs to be directed to the communities to empower the people. Otherwise, political leaders will continue to employ the poor (unemployed) youths as their touts to silence their real or perceived political enemies, thereby causing havoc and political instability in the society as a whole.
3. Proper religious teaching and education should be given participants in various religious groups and each should be made to understand that ethnicity and religion should not be used as weapons of hate and destruction of life and property. This will likely bring a restrain on religious fanatics and thus tame conflicts and violence within the society.
4. The government should ensure that the immediate and remote causes of a crisis, which have been identified (or will be identified) by different judicial inquiry commissions, should be upheld and implemented, while the precipitators of such crisis are brought to trial accordingly. The lessons of each conflict must not be overlooked.

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